

Methods for Copying Painterly or Academic Drawing by Great Artists

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Annotation:

This article attempts to show the importance of methods of copying works of great painters or academic painters, rules and recommendations for copying. The technologies of great artists, the theoretical foundations of copying and its features are discussed.

Keywords: fine art, methods, reproduction sequence.

The system of training teachers-students in the field of fine art in higher educational institutions based on the analysis of fine art samples and familiarization with fine art technology and methods for the correct use of materials related to the science of copying, determines a number of tasks. Various materials can be used for practical classes in painting and drawing. The ability to choose the right materials and objects for each task plays an important role in the success of the picture.

By "copying" we mean the same as in the original. Copying illustrations and drawings "has been practiced since time immemorial. For future artists, a copy of pencils and painting is also important. This method has existed since time immemorial. It is not surprising that in the preparation of students, special attention was paid to copying the originals and gave them enough time. Because unknowingly and inexperiently copying the age of a famous artist can be useless. Therefore, it was necessary to copy the works of masters - artists. It is important to understand the meaning and benefits of this student. To do this, regardless of whether the copied work is an illustration, a pencil or an example of folk arts and crafts, it must first be fully studied in terms of the technology of its execution, processing methods, and then translated into the practical side.

The artists mentoring the great teacher were demanding of their students in this regard. They challenged the student to "correctly translate the work" and taught him "instructions." First, the technique and technology of the functioning of the original work was analyzed and it was predetermined what was necessary for its new reproduction. For example, if a student needed to

copy a work by a famous artist, then before starting the work it was determined how it was drawn on paper. The sequence and technical methods of work will be analyzed. Then all processes were performed in the same way as during the initial work. It takes into account all the features used by the artist.

Copying works of fine art begins with the selection of suitable works of pencil and painting. In this case, the degree of complexity of the selected works should also be taken into account. The work of great artists can be used as an example. This should be repeated, knowing how they work. The artist cannot interpret or change his original work.

If this is possible when copying the Bible, its dimensions must correspond to the original. Otherwise, the process of reducing work or increasing from a small reproduction will not bring benefits, but, on the contrary, will create difficulties. Because what the artist used is difficult to compare with what it really was. When copying paintings, it is also important to follow certain rules. For this, first of all, a sample of the work will be chosen, which the student can "assimilate." Its dimensions are determined, and then a fabric is selected that is 1 1.5 centimeters smaller or larger. This is done depending on which fabric the original was made on. It is important for the copy to select materials and objects, as in the original. Then the original will be similar to the original.

If this is a museum exhibit, a reproduction of which is at hand, then you can make a small drawing by increasing its size on the cells. In this case, the image of the work must be obtained in accordance with the plan. It is also necessary to determine which types of paints were used in the work. It is also important to know that it is made from liquid or dark strokes. The copyist needs not only to make a plan, but also to imitate the style and technique of the artist. The process of copying pictures is as follows:

- the product corresponding to the original purpose is selected;
- a pencil obtained in the immediate vicinity of the original sample is developed;
- fabric is placed on the tag;
- the original is prepared for work in the same way as in technology;
- the main color policy is being prepared;
- first of all, a pencil is applied to the surface of the finished fabric, in which karakaz can be used;
- to avoid rubbing the pencil, brown or "ultramarine" paint is applied over it, making it more liquid;
- after the image is accurate, spells will be performed;
- Gradually, the colors required for the coating will be performed as intended;
- the image shall not be distorted during painting;
- When a larger brush is used first and the image becomes more detailed, it becomes smaller.
- checked for similarity to the original work;
- After the work is completed in all the stipulated requirements, it will be completed and crossed out.

When copying the works of master artists, first of all, you need to pay attention to the exact and accurate execution of the pencil. From several found reproductions of the copied picture, the highest quality and more voluminous specimens are extracted, which are divided into cells of equal size. This allows us to copy the work with precision and do the initial work correctly. Thus, a copy was

created that should have been received. Pupils and learners must learn the scientific, theoretical and practical aspects of "fine art technology." Lacking sufficient knowledge and skills in the field of technology, a student cannot master composition, pencil, painting, sculpture, folk art and other subjects.

It is noteworthy that the works of mature artists impress with the skill of the composition, the relevance of the theme, the combination of hot and cold colors. Most famous painters are primarily pen masters. Among them Bryullov K.P., Shishkin I.I., Makovsky V.E., Polenov V.D., Repin I.E., Rubel M.A., Sherov V.A., Korovin K.A., A.A. Abdullaev, O. Tansikbaev, Z. Inogov, M.N. Abiev, R. Akhmedov, B. Zhalolov, A. Mirzyaev, A. Ikromzhanov, I. Khaidarov.

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